

MULTIFUNCTIONAL SHAPE MEMORY ALLOY TUFTED COMPOSITES

WeeLiam Khor¹, Raj Ladani², Geoffrey Knott¹, Thibaut Buns³,
Andrew D. Foreman⁴, Charlotte Meeks⁴, Alan Steele⁵, Tim
Cooper⁵, Adrian P. Mouritz², Francesco Ciampa^{1*}

wee.khor@surrey.ac.uk

¹University of Surrey, Department of Mechanical Engineering Sciences,
Guildford GU2 7XH, United Kingdom.

²School of Engineering, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia, 3000.

³National Composites Centre, Bristol & Bath Science Park, Emersons
Green, Bristol BS16 7FS, United Kingdom.

⁴QinetiQ, Applied Science, Farnborough GU14 0LX, United Kingdom.

⁵QinetiQ Australia, 210 Kings Way, South Melbourne, Victoria, Australia,
3205

Objectives and outline

1. Manufacturing of SMA tufted composites
2. Characterization:
 - I. Fracture toughness
 - II. Microscopic observations on the specimen
3. Incorporation of SMA functionalities:
 - I. Crack closure
 - II. SMA resistance measurement
 - III. Defect detection by thermography
4. Conclusion and future work

1. Manufacturing of SMA tufted composites

2.i Fracture toughness (Experiment)

» Mode I

- ASTM D5528
- DCB

» Mode II

- ASTM D7905
- ENF

		Fracture toughness, J/m ²
G_I	Plain	645 ± 56
	SMA tufted	2578 ± 586
G_{II}	Plain	2395 ± 69
	SMA tufted	3218 ± 258

2.i Fracture toughness (FEA)

» Cohesive zone model

- Composite
- Tuft

2.i Fracture toughness (FEA)

» Extraction of traction-separation law of the tufts

2.i Fracture toughness (FEA)

» Nitinol SMA properties

Property	Definition	Value	Units
E_A	Young modulus austenite	60	GPa
E_A	Young modulus martensite	60	GPa
ν_m	Poisson's ratio martensite	0.3	
ϵ_{tr}	Transformation strain	7.5	%
σ_{ul}^S	Stress at which transformation begins during loading	520	MPa
σ_{ul}^E	Stress at which transformation ends during loading	600	MPa
σ_{iu}^S	Stress at which reverse transformation begins during unloading	300	MPa
σ_{iu}^E	Stress at which reverse transformation ends during unloading	200	MPa
T	Reference temperature	45	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
$\delta\sigma/\delta T$	Stress versus temperature gradient for loading	12	$\text{MPa}/^{\circ}\text{C}$

2.i Fracture toughness (FEA)

» ASTM D5528-01

Table 1

Elastic properties of the composite material. E and G are the elastic and shear modulus; ν is the Poisson's ratio. The subscripts 1, 2, 3 are the in-plane, transverse and out-of-plane directions in a ply-based coordinate system of fibres, respectively.

Property	Value	Units
E_{11}	60,000	MPa
E_{22}	60,000	MPa
E_{33}	9,500	MPa
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.3	MPa
ν_{23}	0.3	MPa
$G_{12} = G_{13}$	3,900	MPa
G_{23}	2,800	MPa

Table 2

Cohesive material input properties for the composite.

Property	Definition	Value	Units
K_{11}	Penalty stiffness	1×10^5	MPa
K_{22}	Penalty stiffness	1×10^5	MPa
K_{33}	Penalty stiffness	1×10^5	MPa
τ_{33}	Transverse strength	50	MPa
$\tau_{13} = \tau_{23}$	Shear strength	40	MPa
G_{Ic}	Mode I fracture toughness	0.5	kJ/mm ²
$G_{IIc} = G_{IIIc}$	Mode II & III fracture toughness	0.8	kJ/mm ²

2.ii Microscopic observations on the specimen

3.i Crack closure

3.ii SMA resistance measurement

3.iii Defect detection by thermography

- » FLIR A6780 MWIR
- » 3MP resolution
- » 3.0 – 5.0 μm spectral range

3.iii Defect detection by thermography

» Undamaged specimen

3.iii Defect detection by thermography

» Specimen with delamination

3.iii Defect detection by thermography

Heating step

Cooling step

3.iii Defect detection by thermography

» Image processing by PCA

3. Conclusion and future work

» SMA as out of plane reinforcement

- Improvement in delamination resistance
- Useful as heat generator for delamination detection using thermography
- Exhibits shape memory properties when heated to close delamination
- Shows potential as a ‘strain sensor’

» Future work

- Performance evaluation on a structural component, e.g. T-joints
- Quantification of the SMA ‘clamping’ force

